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Additional Supplementary Files

marrellomatrix.nex	Nexus file including Bayes Block
constraints.csv	File containing topological constraints, formatted for TreeSearch
mar.run	TNT script
mar_equal.R	TreeSearch equal weights parsimony script
mar_IW.R	TreeSearch implied weights parsimony script
mar_mono_chel.R	TreeSearch parsimony script, with monophyletic Chelicerata constraint
mar_mand_sist.R	TreeSearch parsimony script, with Mandibulata+Marrellomorpha constraint

Supplementary Table 1. The following is a list of taxa present in Bed 3. The diversity of this “recovery fauna” is lower than at other stages of bioherm development while the overall population was sparse and concentrated in isolated patches around exposed mound tops and associated depressions. Numbers indicate specimens collected across several study plots with a total area of ca. 85x30 meters. Some taxa are present in huge numbers, especially in debris fields and only their presence is recorded.

Group	Taxon	Number of Observations
Trilobites	<i>Gabriceraurus</i>	12
Trilobites	<i>Bufoceraurus</i>	7
Trilobites	Undescribed Cheirurid	16
Trilobites	<i>Ceraurus sp.</i>	22
Trilobites	<i>Ceraurus cf. maewestoides</i>	5
Trilobites	<i>Sceptaspis</i>	2
Trilobites	<i>Isotelus</i>	3
Trilobites	<i>Failleana</i>	8
Trilobites	<i>Flexicalymene</i>	11
Trilobites	<i>Cybeloides</i>	8
Trilobites	<i>Bumastus</i>	16
Trilobites	<i>Dolichoharpes</i>	3
Trilobites	<i>Meadowtownella</i>	2
Trilobites	<i>Raymondites</i>	2
Crinoids	<i>Archaeocrinus</i>	344
Crinoids	<i>Reteocrinus alveolatus</i>	153
Crinoids	<i>Reteocrinus stellaris</i>	21
Crinoids	<i>Grenprisia</i>	12
Crinoids	<i>Cremacrinus</i>	11
Crinoids	<i>Undescribed cladid</i>	31
Crinoids	<i>Carabocrinus</i>	3
Crinoids	<i>Cleiocrinus</i>	5
Crinoids	<i>Praecupulocrinus</i>	12

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Rhombiferans	<i>Glyptocystites</i>	24
Rhombiferans	<i>Pleurocystites</i>	4
Other echinoderms	<i>Astrocystites</i>	33
Other echinoderms	<i>Hybocystites</i>	10
Other echinoderms	<i>Amygdalocystites</i>	2
Other echinoderms	<i>Stenaster</i>	12
Molluscs	orthocerids	14
Molluscs	<i>Hormotoma</i>	Debris fields
Brachiopods	<i>Sowerbyella</i>	Debris fields
Brachiopods	<i>Platystrophia</i>	Debris fields
Brachiopods	<i>Dalmanella</i>	Debris fields
Brachiopods	<i>Strophomena</i>	Debris fields
Brachiopods	Indeterminate lingulid	
Bryozoans	<i>Heterotrypa</i>	
Bryozoans	<i>Hallopora</i>	
Bryozoans	<i>Hemiphragma</i>	
Bryozoans	<i>Constellaria</i>	
Bryozoans	Indeterminate fistuloporid	
Other	Conulariids	23
Other	Receptaculids	37
Other	<i>Spenothallus</i>	1
Other	Indeterminate tube	1
Soft bodied	Macroalgae	4
Soft bodied	Indeterminate carapace	1
Soft bodied	<i>Tomlinsonus dimitrii</i>	1
Trace Fossils	<i>Chondrites</i>	
Trace Fossils	<i>Paleophycus</i>	
Trace Fossils	<i>Thallasinoides</i>	

Re-evaluation of marrellomorph phylogeny

Given the paucity of marrellomorphs in the fossil record, phylogenies focusing on their internal relationships have been scarce. The first reviews come from the works of Kühl et al. (2008) and Kühl & Rust (2010). The first hypothesis supported by a phylogenetic analysis, though, comes from Rak et al. (2013), who included both equal and implied weights Parsimony analyses for six species with a total of 16 newly-defined characters. Marrellomorphs were also included in a dataset encompassing hundreds of panarthropod taxa, with various different iterations (Legg et al., 2013; Legg, 2015, 2016). The final iteration of that dataset which included relevant changes to the coding of Marrellomorpha consisted of 315 taxa (with 10 marrellomorphs) and 752 characters (Legg, 2016). Following these works, Aris et al. (2017) performed the most recent marrellomorph-specific analysis to date, combining characters from previous datasets for a total of 11 marrellomorphs and 53 characters. This last dataset was taken as the starting point for creation of the matrix employed in this paper.

We undertook major revisions to the Aris et al. dataset for a number of reasons, as follows. First, all non-informative (autapomorphic, constant) characters were excluded. Various characters were found to be non-informative in the original dataset or after the exclusion of larval crustaceomorph taxa from our dataset, due to their problematic status as outgroup representatives (C3-6, 8, C10-12, C15-17, 24, 26, 29, C32-35, C37-43, C47-53). While phylogenetic ties between these taxa and marrellomorphs have been previously suggested (Cotton and Braddy, 2004; Legg et al., 2013), the coding of radically different developmental stages in phylogenies is problematic and is ideally avoided (Sharma et al., 2017).

Furthermore, several characters were redefined in order to accommodate new taxa and observations, as well to provide an explicit definition of their coding, sometimes absent in the original publication (C2, 18-20, 25, C27-28, 30, 36, 46). In some cases (e.g. C18-20, related to the primary and secondary spines of the marrellid shield), characters had to be combined, as their perfect correlation indicated character non-independence, which can result in problematic bias (Sereno, 2007). Finally, some characters were excluded, due to uncertainty of observation in the fossil material or absence of sufficiently specific definitions (C7, 31, 44, 45), accidental repetition of the same character (C9 & 13), or homology statements which, in our view, are not well-supported (e.g C21, inferring homology between the secondary spines of marrellids and marginal spines on acerrostracan carapaces).

Supplementary Table 2. List of marrellomorph taxa and outgroups. Dataset abbreviations, used in character list, are noted in the far right column.

Marrellida		
<i>Tomlinsonus dimitrii</i> gen. et sp. nov.	This article	New
<i>Furca bohémica</i>	Rak, Š., Ortega-Hernández, J., & Legg, D. A. (2013). A revision of the Late Ordovician marrellomorph arthropod <i>Furca bohémica</i> from Czech Republic. <i>Acta Palaeontologica Polonica</i> , 58(3), 615-628.	R13
Moroccan Marrellid	Van Roy, P. (2006). Non-Trilobite Arthropods from the Ordovician of Morocco. (Doctoral dissertation, Ghent University). Van Roy, P., Briggs, D. E., & Gaines, R. R. (2015). The Fezouata fossils of Morocco; an extraordinary record of marine life in the Early Ordovician. <i>Journal of the Geological Society</i> , 172(5), 541-549.	
<i>Marrella splendens</i>	Whittington, H. B. (1971). Redescription of <i>Marrella splendens</i> (Trilobitoidea) from the Burgess Shale, Middle Cambrian, British Columbia. <i>Bulletin of Geological Survey of Canada</i> , 209, 1-24. García-Bellido, D. C., & Collins, D. H. (2006). A new study of <i>Marrella splendens</i> (Arthropoda, Marrellomorpha) from the Middle Cambrian Burgess Shale, British Columbia, Canada. <i>Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences</i> , 43(6), 721-742.	
<i>Mimetaster hexagonalis</i>	Kühl, G., & Rust, J. (2010). Re-investigation of <i>Mimetaster hexagonalis</i> : a marrellomorph arthropod from the Lower Devonian Hunsrück Slate (Germany). <i>Paläontologische Zeitschrift</i> , 84(3), 397-411.	
'<i>Mimetaster</i>' florestaensis	Aris, M. J., Corronca, J. A., Quinteros, A. S., & Pardo, P. L. (2016). A new marrellomorph euarthropod from the Early Ordovician of Argentina. <i>Acta Palaeontologica Polonica</i> , v. 62, p. 1-8.	A16
Acercostraca		
<i>Enosiaspis hrungir</i>	Legg, D. A. (2016). An acercostracan marrellomorph (Euarthropoda) from the Lower Ordovician of Morocco. <i>The Science of Nature</i> , 103(3), 21.	L16

<i>Primicaris larvaformis</i>	Zhang, X. L., Han, J., Zhang, Z. F., Liu, H. Q., & Shu, D. G. (2003). Reconsideration of the supposed naraoiid larva from the Early Cambrian Chengjiang Lagerstätte, South China. <i>Palaeontology</i> , 46(3), 447-465.
<i>Skania fragilis</i>	Legg, D. A. (2015). The morphology and affinities of <i>Skania fragilis</i> (Arthropoda) from the middle Cambrian Burgess Shale. <i>Bulletin of Geosciences</i> , 90(3), 509-518.
<i>Xylokorys chledophilia</i>	Siveter, D. J., Fortey, R. A., Sutton, M. D., Briggs, D. E., & Siveter, D. J. (2007). A Silurian ‘marrellomorph’ arthropod. <i>Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences</i> , 274(1623), 2223-2229.
<i>Vachonisia rogeri</i>	Kühl, G., Bergström, J., & Rust, J. (2008). Morphology, Palaeobiology and phylogenetic position of <i>Vachonisia rogeri</i> (Arthropoda) from the Lower Devonian Hunsrück Slate (Germany). <i>Palaeontographica Abteilung A</i> , 286, 123-157.

Partially preserved specimens (not included)

<i>Austromarrella klausmuelleri</i>	Haug, J. T., Castellani, C., Haug, C., Waloszek, D., & Maas, A. (2012). A <i>Marrella</i> -like arthropod from the Cambrian of Australia: A new link between “Orsten”-type and Burgess Shale assemblages. <i>Acta Palaeontologica Polonica</i> , 58(3), 629-639.
<i>Dyrnwynia conollyi</i>	Legg, D. A. (2016). A new marrellid arthropod from the Ordovician of Wales. <i>Acta Palaeontologica Polonica</i> , 61(3), 617-619.
<i>Marrella</i> sp.	Zhao, Y. L., Yuan, J. L., Zhu, M. Y., Yang, X. L., & Peng, J. (2003). The occurrence of the genus <i>Marrella</i> (Trilobitoidea) in Asia. <i>Progress in Natural Science</i> , 13(9), 708-711. Liu, Q. (2013). The First Discovery of <i>Marrella</i> (Arthropoda, Marrellomorpha) from the Balang Formation (Cambrian Series 2) in Hunan, China. <i>Journal of Paleontology</i> , 87(3), 391-394.
<i>Skania? sundbergi</i>	Lin, J. P., Gon, S. M., Gehling, J. G., Babcock, L. E., Zhao, Y. L., Zhang, X. L., Hu, S. X., Yuan, J. L., Yu, M. Y., & Peng, J., 2006, A <i>Parvancorina</i> -like arthropod from the Cambrian of South China: <i>Historical Biology</i> , 18(1), 33-45.

Outgroups

<i>Eoredlichia</i>	Hou, X., E. N. K. Clarkson, J. Yang, X. Zhang, G. Wu, and Z. Yuan. (2008). Appendages of early Cambrian <i>Eoredlichia</i>
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	(Trilobita) from the Chengjiang biota, Yunnan, China. <i>Earth Environ. Sci. Trans. R. Soc. Edinburgh</i> 99, 213–223.	
<i>Aquilonifer</i>	Briggs, D. E., Siveter, D. J., Siveter, D. J., Sutton, M. D., & Legg, D. (2016). Tiny individuals attached to a new Silurian arthropod suggest a unique mode of brood care. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> , 113(16), 4410-4415.	
<i>Waptia</i>	Vannier, J., Aria, C., Taylor, R. S., & Caron, J. B. (2018). <i>Waptia fieldensis</i> Walcott, a mandibulate arthropod from the middle Cambrian Burgess Shale. <i>Royal Society Open Science</i> , 5(6), 172206.	
<i>Tokummia</i>	Aria, C., & Caron, J. B. (2017). Burgess Shale fossils illustrate the origin of the mandibulate body plan. <i>Nature</i> , 545(7652), 89-92.	AC17
<i>Haliestes</i>	Siveter, D. J., Sutton, M. D., Briggs, D. E., & Siveter, D. J. (2004). A Silurian sea spider. <i>Nature</i> , 431(7011), 978-980.	
<i>Palaeoisopus</i>	Bergström, J., W. Stürmer, and G. Winter. (1980). <i>Palaeoisopus</i> , <i>Palaeopantopus</i> and <i>Palaeothea</i> , pycnogonid arthropods from the Lower Devonian Hunsrück Slate, West Germany. <i>Paläontologische Zeitschrift</i> , 54, 7-54.	
<i>Mollisonia</i>	Aria, C., & Caron, J. B. (2019). A middle Cambrian arthropod with chelicerae and proto-book gills. <i>Nature</i> , 573(7775), 586-589.	
<i>Kylinxia</i>	Zeng, H., Zhao, F., Niu, K., Zhu, M., & Huang, D. (2020). An early Cambrian euarthropod with radiodont-like raptorial appendages. <i>Nature</i> , 588(7836), 101-105.	

Phylogenetic Trees

Supplementary Figure 1. Results of equal weights Fitch Parsimony analysis performed in TNT. Numbers at nodes are Jackknife percentages (1000 pseudoreplicates). Tree length = 86.

Supplementary Figure 2. Results of inapplicable-corrected Parsimony analyses performed in the R package *TreeSearch*. Unconstrained analyses with equal and implied weights (sampling a range of concavity values) and equal weights analyses performed with specified outgroup constraints shown. Numbers at nodes are Jackknife percentages (1000 pseudoreplicates). Tree lengths = 89 (unconstrained), 90 (Chelicerata constrained), 93 (Mandibulata+Marrellomorpha constrained).

Supplementary Figure 3 (following page). Results of Bayesian analyses performed in MrBayes. Majority rule consensus and Maximum Clade Credibility (MCC) trees are shown for analyses with specified outgroup constraints. Numbers at nodes are posterior probabilities.

Unconstrained Majority Rule

Unconstrained MCC

Constrained Chelicerata Majority Rule

Constrained Chelicerata MCC

Constrained Mandibulata+Marrellomorpha Majority Rule

Constrained Mandibulata+Marrellomorpha MCC

List of characters

Cephalon

1. Tergal sclerotization of head, type [AC17:34].

- (0) Tergites with posterior expansion, some cephalic tergites can be freely articulating (carapace)
- (1) Tergites with limited expansion, cephalic tergites fused (shield)

Remarks: This character separates the presence of a shield developed from the fusion of cephalic tergites (possibly ancestral to all euarthropods), from an elongated carapace that extends above some cephalic and trunk tergites. The state in acercostracans is debatable. Arguably, since the tergites of the trunk appear to be fused and incorporated into the dorsal covering, this should be considered a combination head shield and pygidium, akin to the condition in e.g. *Tegopelte* (Lin et al., 2006). This certainly seems to be the case in *Skania* and *Primicaris* in which small “genal” spines delimit the boundary between the head and trunk tergites. However, Legg (2015, 2016) has favoured an interpretation of the acercostracan dorsal covering as a carapace, potentially homologous with that of early mandibulates. To test this view, we code acercostracans as state 0, but consider the possibility of trunk fusion in a separate character, below.

2. Cephalon with a frontal rim (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Legg (2016) has suggested homologizing features of the acercostracan carapace and marrellid shield, constituting one of the major apomorphies of Marrellomorpha. In particular, the anterior rim seen in ‘skaniids’ and possibly *Enosiaspis* was compared to the margin of the mediolateral spines in marrellids.

3. Carapace valves [AC17:35].

- (0) Bivalved
- (1) Fused dorsally

Remarks: We argue that the carapace of some acercostracans (e.g. *Xylokorys*) could be considered bivalved in the same sense as in hymenocarines, as both are divided into two lateral sections that are joined at an angle along a dorsal hinge. The “cordiform” shape of the anterior margin of the acercostracan carapace has also been emphasized (Legg, 2016), but this is in fact probably largely due to the 3D geometry of the two valves. This is best seen in *Xylokorys*, in which the carapace is shaped like an inverted V in cross section, such that tilting in the sagittal plane can accentuate or efface the

appearance of a notch (Siveter et al., 2007). This explains the high variability in anterior outline in more compressed specimens of *Enosiaspis* and *Vachonisia*.

4. Carapace valves, type [AC17:38]

- (0) Type I: sub-straight cross-section, covering body dorsally
- (1) Type II: Convex cross-section, enveloping body ventrolaterally

5. Carapace, median ridge [R13:1].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Codes for the unique condition in some acercostracans (e.g. *Vachonisia*, *Xylokorys*). As previously defined, this character also included the presence of a “ventral shelf”, but we consider this here under the separate character coding for a doublure. Applicable only for carapaces.

6. Shield, shape (NEW).

- (0) Subrectangular
- (1) Subhexagonal
- (2) Semicircular

Remarks: Separates the subrectangular central portion of the shield of e.g. *Marrella* or ‘*M.*’ *florestaensis* from the hexagonal shield of e.g. *M. hexagonalis*. Spines are not considered here. State 2 accommodates non-marrellid shields such as that of *Eoredlichia*.

7. Doublure [A16:23].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Here we consider a portion of cuticle from the cephalic shield or carapace (and sometimes also trunk tergites) that folds around the ventral side forming a marginal shelf to constitute a doublure (Cotton and Braddy, 2004; Bitsch and Bitsch, 2007). Although some authors, e.g. (Whittington, 1971), disputed the presence of a doublure in *Marrella*, it is present based on the definition employed here. The “ventral shelf” of some acercostracans also qualifies.

8. Hypostome (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Here hypostome is understood as a ventral plate-like cephalic structure that extends posteriorly, overlying the mouth at its posterior margin and the bases of the frontalmost appendages laterally. Potentially related structures (e.g. labrum, *sensu* Aria et al., 2021) are not considered here.

9. Proboscis [AC17:126].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: This is a pycnogonid apomorphy.

10. Spines on the cephalic shield (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Here we test the homology of the spines in marrellomorphs with the genal spines of various arachnomorphs. These two are demarcated in other characters below. The identity of spines in marrellids and *Skania* as genal spines has been disputed (Legg, 2015) on the basis of their supposed “pre-appendicular” origin, however it is not clear how precisely this could be assessed. We see no justification for excluding this *a priori* as a potential homology.

11. Anterolateral spines [A16:19].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Codes for the frontalmost pair of spines present in mimetasterids. These have also been recognized in a single specimen of *Marrella splendens*, (Whittington, 1971). Van Roy (2006) interpreted the specimen as an example of an atavistic mutant, but considering that it is not presently certain whether anterolateral spines were present in the ancestral marrellid this assessment is premature. Nonetheless it is clear this individual represents an abnormal form and thus we code *Marrella* as state 0.

12. Anterolateral spines, shape (NEW).

- (0) Straight
- (1) Curved

Remarks: Differentiates the state (0) in e.g. *M. hexagonalis* and *M. florestaensis* from that in the e.g. Moroccan marrellid (1).

13. Anterolateral spines, relative length (NEW).

- (0) Subequal to mediolateral and posterolateral

- (1) Less than half as long as mediolateral and posterolateral

Remarks: Differentiates the relatively short spines of e.g. *M. florestaensis* or *F. bohémica* from the relatively longer ones in e.g. *M. hexagonalis* and the Moroccan marrellid.

14. Mediolateral and posterolateral spines with secondary spines [A16:20, R13:2].

- (0) Absent
(1) Present

Remarks: Non-marrellids with genal spines are coded absent. Mediolateral and posterolateral spines are present together in all known marrellids (except where ambiguous) and thus may not represent independent characters. We therefore code them in a single character. We do, however, consider the possible homology of genal spines in various arachnomorphs with either mediolateral or posterolateral spines in a sovereign character (Ch. 10). Secondary spines are also invariably present in marrellids, either in the form of rows of digitiform outgrowths lining the three pairs of cephalic spines in mimetasterids or the shorter triangular projections on the posterolateral spines of *Marrella*. We coded *Tomlinsonus* as state 1 even though the posterolateral spines are not visible.

15. Posterolateral spines, relative length (NEW).

- (0) <1.5 times the length of the central shield
(1) >1.5 times the length of the central shield

Remarks: Differentiates the long spines in e.g. *M. splendens* or the Moroccan marrellid from the relatively short ones in e.g. *F. bohémica*. We also considered adding an equivalent character for the mediolateral spines, but this was not as variable or readily discretizable.

16. Secondary spines on anterolateral spines, number along anterior margin (NEW).

- (0) 10 or fewer
(1) More than 10

Remarks: Differentiates the state (0) in e.g. *M. hexagonalis* from that in e.g. the Moroccan marrellid (1).

Head characters

17. Lateral compound eyes [R13:7].

- (0) Absent
(1) Present

Remarks: Marrellomorphs generally do not have compound eyes, however putative eyes with segmented stalks have been identified in *M. hexagonalis* (Kühl and Rust, 2010).

Cephalic appendages

18. Post-ocular segments incorporated into the head tagma, number [A16:25].

- (0) 2
- (1) 3
- (2) 4
- (3) 5
- (4) 7

Remarks: *Marrella* is here considered to have only 2 cephalic appendage pairs (Whittington, 1971), whereas *Mimetaster* has 3 (Kühl and Rust, 2010). *Vachonisia* and *Xylokorys* have 5 (Siveter et al., 2007; Kühl et al., 2008), but only 4 appear to be present in *Enosiaspis* (Legg, 2016). We follow (Dunlop and Lamsdell, 2017) in coding 4 post-ocular head segments in pycnogonids.

19. Cephalic endopods, maximum number of podomeres (NEW).

- (0) <7
- (1) 7
- (2) >7

Remarks: Codes for the maximum number of podomeres present in any cephalic endopod. The antennules/chelicerae are excluded from consideration.

20. Frontalmost appendage a chelicera, i.e. chelate or subchelate with only two opposing faces [AC17:72].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: The incomplete frontalmost appendage of *Xylokorys* might be chelate (Siveter et al., 2007), but given the poor preservation we chose to be conservative in not considering this as a chelicera. We follow Briggs et al. (2016) in tentatively considering the chelate appendages as the second pair of appendages in *Aquilonifer*.

21. Antennule, length (NEW).

- (0) Short (subequal to head length or shorter)
- (1) Long (substantially longer than head length)

Remarks: The antennules of marrellids are much longer than those of acercostracans.

22. All cephalic endopods are developed [cf. AC17:86].

- (0) Some are highly reduced
- (1) All are developed

Remarks: Mandibulates are characterized by the reduction of cephalic endopods. This condition is considered distinct from the loss of entire appendages, as in the intercalary segment of some mandibulates, considered in the following character. The identity of the uniramous, setate second appendage of *M. splendens* as an endopod or exopod is uncertain, as it somewhat resembles the exopods of *Vachonisia* (see discussion below). By comparison, the uniramous head appendages of *M. hexagonalis* and *T. dimitrii*, might also be exopod homologues, although nothing in their morphology specifically supports this (Rak et al., 2013). Alternatively, in these taxa, the general stenopodous morphology and the presence of enditic spines – on the subterminal podomere of the second appendage and more proximally on the third – resembles the trunk appendages and their endites, suggestive of an endopodal homology for the cephalic appendages. Developmental evidence suggests that the transition from biramy to uniramy can be accomplished by suppression of the splitting of the outgrowing appendage axis, rather than loss of one ramus (Wolff and Scholtz, 2008). Such a process might explain the combination of endopod and exopod-like morphologies in the marrellid post-antennular appendage. In this character we adopt the endopodal interpretation for *M. hexagonalis* and *T. dimitrii*, but we code *M. splendens* as ambiguous and consider the possible homology of its bands of setae with those on the exopods of acerrostracans below.

23. Second cephalic appendage [AC17: 91].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: State 0 designates the intercalary segment which is considered to be widely present in early mandibulates (Aria and Caron, 2017a; Vannier et al., 2018; Aria et al., 2021).

24. Second cephalic appendage, ramification (NEW).

- (0) Uniramous
- (1) Biramous

Remarks: Acerrostracans notably have biramous cephalic appendages while those in marrellids are uniramous.

25. Developed second cephalic appendage differentiated (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Several taxa have appendage differentiation defined by more than just a transition to uniramy, so this character is considered independent from the previous character.

26. Second cephalic appendage hypertrophied with tarsus-like termination (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: State 1 accommodates *M. hexagonalis* and *Tomlinsonus*. The Moroccan marrellid also has a somewhat similar appendage, but because it is considerably smaller than in the former two taxa we code it as state 0.

27. Second cephalic appendage, termination (NEW).

- (0) Multiple claws
- (1) Blade-like podomere with setae
- (2) Single elongate spine

Remarks: Most early euarthropods have endopods terminating in multiple claws. In marrellids, the terminal podomere of the second appendage may be a straight spine as in *Tomlinsonus* or modified into a broad blade as in *Marrella* (García-Bellido and Collins, 2006). In *Mimetaster hexagonalis* the terminal podomere has been interpreted to be subdivided (Stürmer and Bergström, 1976), although this is not very clear in the x-radiograph images. We consider it under state 2 here.

28. Some post-antennular cephalic endopods, chelate or subchelate [R13:11].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: This condition is present in *Vachonisia* and *Xylokorys*, as well as some pycnogonids and *Aquilonifer*. The chelate appendages of *Tokummia* originate from a post-cephalic segment.

29. Setal brush on any cephalic appendage (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Kühl et al. (2008) compared the long, setiferous exopods of *Xylokorys* and *Vachonisia*. Similar elongate exopods, though bearing fewer distal setae, are also present in *Primicaris*. The uniramous second appendage of *Marrella* also bears distal setae. We coded *Marrella* as state 1 to see if the setal brush could be optimized as homologous with those of acerrostracans, implying homology with the acerrostracan exopod.

30. Mandible (protopod of third limb-bearing segment subdivided with proximal gnathobasic elaboration, constituting main feeding limb of adult head) [A16:39].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

31. Third appendage, ramification (NEW).

- (0) Uniramous
- (1) Biramous

Remarks: In *Marrella* the third appendage is biramous, but in other marrellids it is uniramous, demonstrating some independent variability from the ramification of the second appendage. We note that in *Marrella* the third appendage does not appear to be incorporated into the head.

32. Antenniform fifth appendage [L16, A16:14].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: This character codes for the unique condition in *Vachonisia* and *Xylokorys*, where the fifth appendage is antenniform.

Trunk-related characters

33. Multisegmented trunk [A16:30].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Multisegmentation is here defined as the presence of more than 20 trunk segments.

34. Multisegmentation, number of segments (NEW).

- (0) 20-29
- (1) 30-34
- (2) >34

Remarks: Most marrellomorphs for which a reliable trunk segment count can be made have 30-34. *Marrella* has notably fewer (26-7) while *Vachonisia* has many more (ca. 80).

35. Tergopleural rings [AC17:153].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Codes for the fusion of tergites and pleurites into rings that are flush with the body, rather than extending ventrally or laterally. This condition is typical of some mandibulates like hymenocarines, but is also seen in marrellids (Aria and Caron, 2017a).

36. Trunk tergites, fusion (NEW).

- (0) All trunk tergites freely articulating
- (1) Some tergites fused (pygidium)

Remarks: While we opted to code *Skania* and *Primicaris* as possessing a carapace (e.g. Legg, 2015, contra Lin et al., 2006), it seems probable that their continuous tergum incorporates fused trunk tergites, posterior to the “genal” spines. In *Primicaris* these tergites extend laterally into small spines, while in *Skania* underlying diverticulae are segmentally arranged. We therefore coded the presence of trunk fusion for these taxa. The conditions in *Vachonisia*, *Xylokorys*, and *Enosiaspis* are more ambiguous and we coded these taxa as uncertain, accordingly.

37. Trunk endopods, number of podomeres (NEW).

- (0) <7
- (1) 7
- (2) >7

Remarks: Marrellomorphs tend to have fewer than 7 podomeres in their trunk endopods. This is a departure from the typical heptapodomeran condition found in most early euarthropods (Aria, 2019).

38. Endites on endopods (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Marrellomorph trunk appendages are typified by blunt-tipped endites (Rak et al., 2013).

39. Endopodal endites, type [A16:41].

- (0) Spiniform
- (1) Rounded

Remarks: *Xylokorys* and *Vachonisia* have rounded, swollen, ellipsoidal endites. These can be contrasted with the thinner, more spiniform endites typical of marrellids.

40. Gnathobasic basipod on any appendage (NEW).

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: The development of a gnathobasic basipod is a potentially important apomorphy of Arachnomorpha (Aria and Caron, 2017b). Gnathobases are absent in marrellids, but Siveter et al. (2007) noted the presence of putative gnathobases on the cephalic appendages of *Xylorkorys*.

41. Exopod, size relative to endopod (NEW).

- (0) Exopod shorter than endopod
- (1) Exopod larger than endopod

Remarks: *Vachonisia* and *Xylorkorys* are notably characterized by extremely large trunk exopods, together taking on a conical shape and surrounding the relatively reduced endopods (Kühl et al., 2008).

42. Exopod, subdivision (NEW).

- (0) Three or fewer podomeres
- (1) More than three podomeres

Remarks: Multipodomerous exopods appear to be shared by all marrellids and are assumed to be present in acercostracans. This character has also been proposed to be important in uniting marrellomorphs with mandibulates (Cotton and Braddy, 2004), however, the validity and significance of this character have been questioned. Notably, in Orsten larval crustaceomorphs, multipodomerous exopods are confined to the head, whereas in marrellomorphs they occur in the trunk (Haug et al., 2012). That the Orsten taxa are unknown from adult developmental stages also makes their use as a marrellomorph outgroup non-ideal. The adult hymenocarine *Waptia* has multipodomerous thoracic appendages, however these arguably represent modifications of the endopod (Vannier et al., 2018), so we code *Waptia* as uncertain. Finally, it is worth emphasizing that highly subdivided exopods are also found among arachnomorphs, with the trunk exopods of e.g. *Triarthrus* being particularly similar in morphology (Whittington and Almond, 1987). Related to this, the position of setae/lamellae on the medial rather than lateral face of the exopod, has been proposed as a mandibulate-marrellomorph synapomorphy (Cotton and Braddy, 2004). We omit this here because it is difficult to code for many taxa and the laterally directed state would have been autapomorphic with the outgroups we included.

Termination

43. Telson [A16:33].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present

Remarks: Aria and Caron (2017a) coded a telson as absent in *Marrella*, presumably because the trunk terminates in a small segment with no observable differentiation. We follow this approach here for marrellomorphs in general.

44. Caudal rami [AC17:204].

- (0) Absent
- (1) Present.

Remarks: No appendage-like structures are associated with the posterior termination in any known marrellomorphs.

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